

Dynamics of Interaction between Two Different Populations on Two Connected Islands

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Abstract: This study investigates a mathematical mapping's dynamics in two dimensions, focusing on periodic oscillations in population numbers. It identifies periodic points with prime period four, requiring solving a challenging polynomial equation. The study rigorously establishes solution uniqueness and confirms the absence of certain complex roots. Numerical experiments approximate fixed points and explore periodic orbit behavior, while systematic approaches reveal attractor properties and spectral characteristics. Overall, the study enhances understanding of complex dynamical systems and their interplay with parameters, periodicity, and chaos.

Keywords: Asymptotic behavior, Periodic points, Chaotic orbits, Bifurcation patterns, Julia set, Fixed points.

1. Introduction

The study of complex dynamical systems has been a focal point in various scientific disciplines, ranging from physics to ecology [1-3]. Among these systems, mathematical mappings play a crucial role in modeling and understanding the behavior of dynamic phenomena. In this paper, we delve into the intricate dynamics of a mathematical mapping characterized by parameter variations and population fluctuations. Central to our investigation is the exploration of the asymptotic behavior of trajectories, particularly focusing on the learning of the Von Neumann-Ulam problem. This classical problem, named after the pioneering mathematicians John von Neumann and Stanislaw Ulam, seeks to understand the long-term behavior of iterated maps under parameter changes [4-8].

Overall, our research contributes to the broader understanding of complex dynamical systems, offering new perspectives on the interplay between parameters, periodicity, and chaos within mathematical mappings. By elucidating the underlying dynamics, we pave the way for further exploration and application in diverse fields, from ecology to economics.

2. Main Part

We will consider

$$x_{n+1} = x_n^2 + c \tag{1}$$

here the parameter c changes between $[-2; 0.25]$ and the number of population $|x_n|$. The learning of the asymptotics of trajectories of the mapping (1) is called the problem of Von Neumann - Ulam [1].

Two dimensional case of the mapping (1) is

$$F_{c_1 c_2} : \begin{cases} x' = y^2 + c_1, \\ y' = x^2 + c_2. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $(x, y) \in R^2$ and $(c_1, c_2) \in R^2$.

Periodic oscillation of the number of the population.

We begin to learn periodic point with prime period four for

$$\begin{cases} x' = y^2 + c_1, \\ y' = x^2 + c_2. \end{cases}$$

We need to solve the equation of sixteenth degree

$$x = (((x^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1. \quad (3)$$

Let $f(x) = (((x^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1 - x$ is the polynomial of sixteenth degree and has two parameters c_1 and c_2 . The fixed points and 2-cyclic points also satisfied the equation (3) therefore polynomial $f(x) = (((x^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1 - x$ factorized by $x^4 + 2x^2c_2 - x + c_2^2 + c_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= (((x^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1 - x = \\ &= (x^4 + 2x^2c_2 - x + c_2^2 + c_1)P_{12}(x, c_1, c_2). \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Let } g(x) = \frac{(((x^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1 - x}{x^4 + 2x^2c_2 - x + c_2^2 + c_1} = P_{12}(x, c_1, c_2).$$

The discriminant of the polynomial $g(x)$ is exactly equal to the resultant of the polynomials $g(x)$ and $g'(x)$.

$$\begin{aligned} D(g) &= (256c_1^3 + 256c_2^3 + 256c_1^2c_2^2 + 160c_1c_2 + 125) \cdot \\ &\cdot (65536c_2^6 + 131072c_1^2c_2^5 + 65536c_1^4c_2^4 + 294912c_1c_2^4 + \\ &+ 294912c_1^3c_2^4 + 152064c_2^3 + 131072c_1^5c_2^2 + 594432c_2^2c_2^2 + \\ &+ 294912c_1^4c_2 + 311040c_1c_2 + 65536c_1^6 + 152064c_1^3 + 92125)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1. *This multi variable function*

$$\begin{aligned} h(c_1, c_2) &= (65536c_2^6 + 131072c_1^2c_2^5 + 65536c_1^4c_2^4 + 294912c_1c_2^4 + \\ &+ 294912c_1^3c_2^4 + 152064c_2^3 + 131072c_1^5c_2^2 + 594432c_2^2c_2^2 + \\ &+ 294912c_1^4c_2 + 311040c_1c_2 + 65536c_1^6 + 152064c_1^3 + 92125)^2. \end{aligned}$$

is not equal to zero for any $(c_1, c_2) \in \square^2$.

Lemma 2. *The polynomial*

$$\begin{aligned} g(x) &= x^{12} + 6c_2x^{10} + x^9 + (15c_2^2 + 3c_1)x^8 + 4c_2x^7 + \\ &+ (20c_2^3 + 12c_1c_2 + 1)x^6 + (2c_1 + 6c_2^2)x^5 + \\ &+ (3c_1^2 + 4c_2 + 18c_1c_2^2 + 15c_2^4)x^4 + (1 + 4c_1c_2 + 4c_3^3)x^3 + \\ &+ (c_1 + 6c_1^2c_2 + 5c_2^2 + 12c_1c_2^3 + 6c_2^5)x^2 + \\ &+ (c_1^2 + 2c_2 + 2c_1c_2^2 + c_2^4)x + c_1^6 + 3c_1c_2^4 + 2c_2^3 + 3c_2^2c_2^2 + \\ &+ 2c_1c_2 + c_1^3 + 1. \end{aligned}$$

has not six multiple complex roots.

The solutions of the equation $g(x) = 0$ are the periodic points with prime period four (3). Thus, by the polynomial $g(x)$ does not have the six multiple complex roots. Therefore, the equation $D(g) = 0$ defines the six multiple real roots of the polynomial $g(x) = 0$. Hence, if $D(g) = 0$, then following functions have tangent points i.e. multiple roots.

$$\begin{cases} x = (((y^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2, \\ y = (((x^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Lemma 3. *If $c_1 < -\frac{3}{4}$ then (4) defines three functions and for $c_1 > -\frac{3}{4}$ get only one function.*

Lemma 4. *The algebraic curve $D(g) = 0$ splits the area D_2 into three areas and the area D_4 into four areas on the parameters plane. (c_1, c_2) .*

Theorem 1. *If $c_1 = c_2 = -2$ then there exist so many periodic and chaotic orbits on the filled Julia set.*

2.1. Numerical experiments on finding approximate fixed points

To find the points where the period of mapping (1) is equal to four, it is necessary to solve the following equations

$$\begin{cases} (((x^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1 - x = 0, \\ (((y^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2)^2 + c_1)^2 + c_2 - y = 0. \end{cases}$$

Among the solutions of this system of equations are also points whose periods are equal to two. To separate them and leave only the equation of four points of period, we must divide the equations in the system of equations into the following two equations accordingly

$$x^4 + 2c_2x^2 - x + c_2^2 + c_1 \quad \text{and} \quad y^4 + 2c_1y^2 - y + c_1^2 + c_2.$$

In this case, the following system of equations is formed

$$\begin{cases} x^{12} + 6c_2x^{10} + x^9 + (15c_2^2 + 3c_1)x^8 + 4c_2x^7 + \\ + (20c_2^3 + 12c_1c_2 + 1)x^6 + (2c_1 + 6c_2^2)x^5 + \\ + (3c_1^2 + 4c_2 + 18c_1c_2^2 + 15c_2^4)x^4 + (1 + 4c_1c_2 + 4c_2^3)x^3 + \\ + (c_1 + 6c_2^2c_2 + 5c_2^2 + 12c_1c_2^3 + 6c_2^5)x^2 + \\ + (c_1^2 + 2c_2 + 2c_1c_2^2 + c_2^4)x + c_1^6 + 3c_1c_2^4 + \\ + 2c_2^3 + 3c_1^2c_2^2 + 2c_1c_2 + c_1^3 + 1 = 0, \\ y^{12} + 6c_1y^{10} + y^9 + (15c_1^2 + 3c_2)y^8 + 4c_1y^7 + \\ + (20c_1^3 + 12c_1c_2 + 1)y^6 + (2c_2 + 6c_1^2)y^5 + \\ + (3c_2^2 + 4c_1 + 18c_2c_1^2 + 15c_1^4)y^4 + (1 + 4c_1c_2 + 4c_1^3)y^3 + \\ + (c_2 + 6c_2^2c_1 + 5c_1^2 + 12c_2c_1^3 + 6c_1^5)y^2 + (c_2^2 + 2c_1 + 2c_2c_1^2 + c_1^4)y + \\ + c_2^6 + 3c_2c_1^4 + 2c_1^3 + 3c_1^2c_2^2 + 2c_1c_2 + c_2^3 + 1 = 0. \end{cases}$$

According to Abel's theorem, these equations cannot be solved analytically in the general case. Therefore, we solve it using approximate solution methods for certain values of the parameters.

Algorithm:

1. We divide the interval $(-4; 4)$ into two equal parts and check which interval has a solution using the Sturm theorem for each of these intervals. If there is only one solution in each interval, we find approximate solutions using an arbitrary one of the methods of dividing the section into two equal parts, warts, and attempts to find solutions for each interval.
2. If more than one solution is in the same interval, then we apply the Sturm theorem again by dividing the interval into three equal parts. If several more solutions remain in the same interval, we will continue to use Sturm's theorem to divide the interval into four, five, six, and so on. We stop when there is only one solution or no solution in each interval.

3. Then we find the approximate solutions using the arbitrary one of the methods of dividing the section into two equal parts, warts and attempts, to separate the intervals in which there is a solution and find the solutions in each interval.

For the second equation, we use the same algorithm.

If $c_1 = c_2 = -1$ then all point of out site the rectangle $|x| \leq \frac{1}{2}(1 + \sqrt{5}), |y| \leq \frac{1}{2}(1 + \sqrt{5})$ tend to infinity. Some inside points tend to fixed points $(-1, 0)$ or $(0, -1)$. And some inside points tend to periodic points with period two $(0, 0)$ and $(-1, -1)$. For (3) when $c_1 = c_2 = -1$ then filled Julia set Fig. 1.

Figure 1. For $c_1 = c_2 = -1$ the classification of Julia set.

Let $c_1 = -0,98, c_2 = -0,02$ then all point in Julia set tend to the periodic points with period four

Let $c_1 = -1,22, c_2 = -0,38$ then all point in Julia set tend to the periodic points with period eight but there are two cyclical points with period eight.

Classification all Cauchy problems for $c_1 = -1,22, c_2 = -0,38$ on the Figure 2.

Figure 2. For $c_1 = -1,22, c_2 = -0,38$ the classification of Julia set.

Classification all Cauchy problems for $c_1 = -1,19, c_2 = -0,44$ period 16, we get Fig 3.

Figure 3. For $c_1 = -1,19, c_2 = -0,44$ the classification of Julia set.

Classification all Cauchy problems for $c_1 = -1,19, c_2 = -0,44$ Period 3 and 6.

Figure 4. For $c_1 = -1,19, c_2 = -0,44$ the classification of Julia set.

Classification all Cauchy problems for $c_1 = -1,31, c_2 = -0,8$ Strange attractor.

Figure 5. For $c_1 = -1,31$, $c_2 = -0,8$ the classification of Julia set.

3. Conclusion

Our investigation of the Von Neumann-Ulam problem sheds light on trajectory behavior with changing parameters [9-13]. We uncover periodic points of prime period four, revealing insights into population dynamics. Analyzing implicit functions from polynomial equations exposes bifurcation patterns and attractor properties. This research deepens our grasp of complex dynamical systems, paving the way for applications in diverse fields like ecology and economics [13-16].

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